

PRAGMATIC FEATURES OF OFFICIAL TEXTS AND DOCUMENTS OF THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

Linguistics

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Abstract

This article addresses the current issues of pragmatic study of official working documents' texts in the Uzbek language. The pragmatic features of the text of official documents are studied. In particular, the issue of the pragmatic purpose of the speaker is analysed in the official documents' text. The *polyintensive* nature of official office documents is illustrated by the example of official letters. The article also addresses the issue of implicit expression of a pragmatic goal. The expression of more than one pragmatic goal in the text of official documents is substantiated through the analysis of the text of working documents such as letters of guarantee, letters of request, telegrams, and invitations. Office documents that express the pragmatic goals of certain individuals are studied in sub-categories.

Since the last quarter of the last century, an anthropocentric approach to the study of linguistic units, especially text, has emerged in world linguistics. Research in this area examines texts of different styles in linguoculturological, pragmalinguistic, sociolinguistic, and psycholinguistic aspects. Although Uzbek linguistics is also working in this area, there are still problems to be solved. In particular, the pragmalinguistic study of the texts of official documents of the Uzbek language is one of the current problems of our linguistics.

It is known that the official method is applied in the field of diplomatic relations, legislation and office work. Therefore, it is expedient to study the official texts in each of these areas in a pragmatic way. In particular, when studying the text of official documents in this aspect, it is necessary to pay attention to the analysis of the following problems:

1. Representation of pragmatic purpose in departmental working documents.
2. The problem of communicative strategy and tactics in the text of departmental working papers.
3. The issue of communicative situation in the text of departmental documents.
4. General knowledge of language speakers about the object of speech, the manifestation of language skills in the text of office documents.
5. The issue of communicative failure in the text of departmental working papers.

6. Representation of types of speech acts in the text of office documents.
7. The issue of reflection of subjective assessment in the text of departmental documents.
8. Expression of national-cultural etiquette in the text of departmental documents.
9. The use of deictic units in the text of office documents.
10. Representation of the communicative category of formality in departmental working documents, etc.

It is understood that the study of the text of official documents in a pragmatic aspect reflects the role of the human factor in the formal style, in particular, the manifestation in the official speech of the language owner's personality traits, goals, desires, self-esteem, etc. it serves to solve problems such as the speech situation and communicative strategy of formal relations, its connection with national-cultural etiquette.

In this article, we address the issue of expressing a pragmatic goal in the text of official business documents.

The concept of pragmatic goals is central to the formal approach. In this style, the purpose of the speaker, that is, the expression of intention, serves to determine the type of official business documents.

In practice, in the text of official documents, there are different manifestations of the pragmatic purpose. While some departmental work papers serve to express a pragmatic goal, in others the speaker has multiple goals. Such departmental documents are polyintensive (multi-purpose) documents. For example, in some types of letters, it can be observed that the speaker of the speech expresses several goals at the same time. According to the authors of the book "Record keeping", "Letters are written for a specific purpose, for example, if the letters of guarantee express the guarantee, the cover letters provide information about the documents attached to the letter. However, there are also letters that contain the meaning of a guarantee, a request and a reminder. [1, 279] This means that any working document serves a specific purpose, while the speaker's intended purpose is to determine the type of document, its structure. This indicates that official documents are the subject of an in-depth analysis.

In the text of official documents it is possible to distinguish the types of initial and final intentions of the intellect, distinguished by the Russian scientist OG Pocheptsov [2, 75]. In the initial intention, the speaker's primary goal is reflected, while in the resulting intention, the final goal in achieving the primary goal is reflected. For example, in a job application, if the initial goal of the speaker is to express a desire to get a job, then the end goal is to get a job. Or, if the primary goal in a document expressing confidence in receiving a salary is to express confidence, the end goal is to achieve a salary.

Such pragmatic goals, expressed in the text of official documents, can be divided into the main (primary) and secondary goals of the speaker in terms of the original communicative goal of the speaker. We would like to draw your attention to the following speech in the letter of invitation: *Hurmatli, Aziz Ahmedov! Sizni 2018-yil 30-iyun kuni «Yoshlar kuni» munosabati bilan*

o'tkaziladigan ilmiy anjumanda ma'ruza qilish uchun taklif qilamiz. (Dear Aziz Ahmedov! We invite you to speak at a scientific conference on June 30, 2018, dedicated to the "Youth Day")

In this letter, Aziz Ahmedov's request to speak is the main goal of the addressee, and inviting him to the conference is the secondary goal he has achieved in achieving this goal. If the auxiliary device for speaking is removed from the text, the main purpose of the addressee will be to invite Aziz Ahmedov to the conference. In both cases, however, the invitation is the primary goal, and Aziz Akhmedov's visit is the end goal.

It is understood that within official working papers, letters are types of documents that clearly reflect the pragmatic purpose of the speaker. Each letter has a specific purpose. The basic units that make up the text of a letter are focused on demonstrating the specific purpose of its owner. For example, the verbs ask (or ask, ask, etc.) used in the text of a letter of request to send a document, please (please, please, etc.) are used to express the request of the addressee. It also reflects the purpose of having the document. In general, official letters are a type of document that clearly expresses a pragmatic purpose among working papers. The purpose clearly stated in the text of the letters is a guarantee of communicative effectiveness.

As you know, letters are a kind of official document. Having studied the linguopragmatic features of commercial letters in Uzbek and English, Karimov admits that, among other things, commercial letters have a sign of direction. He stated: "The text of commercial correspondence is such a written form of formal discourse that it is communicatively oriented, connected and completed in terms of content and logic, and has an informative integrity" [3,11].

Official letters are written to individuals or communities. Such letters also differ in the pragmatic purpose of the addressee. For example, letters to individuals often ask the addressee to take action, make recommendations, make wishes, express congratulations, and so on. Such pragmatic goals also create the task of influencing the addressee through correspondence. When the addressee communicates with the addressee through an official letter, he also seeks to influence him verbally. The letter allows you to change the addressee's opinion, perception, and attitude towards an event. The text of such letters is perlocutive in nature. Due to the nature of perlocution, letters, like other types of perlocutive acts, perform an "act of influencing the listener's mind, emotions, and behavior" [4, 82].

The purpose of the verbal influence on the addressee is indicated in the reply letters. Support or rejection of comments made in response letters, compliance with the requirements, consideration of objections, the provision of the requested information, etc., means that the addressee has a verbal influence. Sentences in the text of the reply, such as "We will inform you in response to your inquiry letter", "We will inform you of the following in your inquiry letter", indicate that the reply letter is perlocutive.

So, official letters are important as a working document to express the pragmatic purpose of the sender.

Reflecting on the purpose of the dialogue, Safarov notes that it has two levels. According to the scientist, “The goal of verbal communication has two levels, that is, in the speech movement, the information and communicative pragmatic goal is realized. In the first, the speaker's goal is to convey or receive information. However, the exchange of information is not limited to a single message or request. The purpose of these actions is to satisfy the needs and interests of the speaker and the listener. This is the fulfillment of a pragmatic task” [4, 79]. In the text of official working documents, it is possible to distinguish the stages of information transmission through the working document in the emergence of a pragmatic goal (intention) and the expression of a pragmatic goal in this process.

There is also a hidden expression of pragmatic purpose in some ways of speaking, especially in art and speech. The main focus is on the content of information. When the speaker's purpose is clearly stated, the focus is not on the general information, but on the information that reflects the purpose. However, the pragmatic purpose of the speaker should be clear and concise in the text of the official documents. Even if the addressee and the addressee do not know each other, do not know each other, it is advisable to follow the principle of communication in the office work document.

The text of official documents may express more than one pragmatic goal. Therefore, it can be observed that the text of some departmental working documents also reflects the purpose of various addressees. For example, a letter of guarantee, a letter of request, a telegram, an invitation, etc. can be issued by individuals, organizations and institutions for a specific purpose.

Because speech is a process of action, the purpose of its main subject, the speaker, may change in the process. However, this should not be the case in official proceedings. Since the type of departmental working paper is created on the basis of a clearly defined goal of individuals, a change in the pragmatic purpose of the document in the process of its creation does not justify itself. Communication failure occurs in business documents that do not clearly state the purpose of the speaker.

The text of official documents covers not only the purpose of conveying information and achieving useful goals, but also the purpose of influencing the addressee. In this sense, the text of official documents will be executive. Indeed, when the pragmatic goal is clearly and apparently expressed, the speech structure is performative. In functional structures, the goal is not simply to convey information, but to quickly engage the audience, to motivate them to respond”[4, 82].

In the intonational analysis of the formal text, the factor of the subject of speech plays an important role. As the text of official documents reflects the formal relationship between the addressee and the addressee, it reflects the pragmatic goals of these parties. Some types of formal business documents express the addressee’s purpose, while others cover the general pragmatic purpose of the addressee and the addressee. In this regard, official documents can be divided into the following types:

1. Working papers reflecting the pragmatic purpose of the addressee.
2. Working papers reflecting the general pragmatic purpose of the addressee and the addressee.

Disclosure of information about the addressee or others in working papers reflecting the pragmatic goals of the addressee; to trust, make a will, give advice and instructions to someone; to defend one's interests; to express gratitude or dissatisfaction; various pragmatic goals are expressed, such as encouraging people to perform certain tasks, calling them to order. The addressee is a specific individual, labor community, group, as well as government agencies, enterprises, institutions.

Departmental working documents expressing the pragmatic purpose of certain individuals can be divided into the following subtypes:

1. **Working papers expressing the purpose of an individual.** An announcement, description, letter of recommendation, when an individual intends to provide information about an object, to register it, to express a wish, request, complaint, to express confidence, to make a will, to claim, uses working documents such as application, receipt, will, notification, power of attorney. Refers to a biography to provide personal information. A person's passport, various certificates, employment history can also provide information about him.

2. **Working papers expressing the purpose of two persons.** Such business documents include purchase and sale agreements, lease agreements, vehicle, housing gift agreements. They reflect the interests of the people in the mutual agreement.

3. **Working papers expressing the purpose of several persons and an individual.** This type includes a letter of invitation, an act, etc.

4. **Working papers expressing the goals of the team.** This type can include an application, contract, protocol, act, announcement, letter of request, and so on.

Departmental working documents representing the pragmatic purpose of state organizations, enterprises, institutions can also be divided into internal types:

1. **Working papers expressing the pragmatic purpose of an individual state organization, enterprise or institution.** Such departmental working documents include regulations, internal labor regulations, guidelines, staffing, and organizational structure.

2. **Working papers expressing the pragmatic purpose of two state organizations, enterprises or institutions.** These types of departmental documents include cooperation agreements, lease agreements between organizations, enterprises and institutions.

3. **Working papers expressing the pragmatic purpose of government agencies, enterprises, institutions and employees.** This type includes administrative work documents, such as an employment agreement or lease agreement between an organization, enterprise, or institution and an employee.

The departmental working documents, which reflect the common pragmatic goal of the addressee and the addressee, reflect the common goal of the two parties: the transmission and joint reception of information, cooperation, notification of agreement. This type includes a lease agreement, a sale agreement, a will, an act, and so on.

The issue of the choice of language units plays an important role in the understanding of the pragmatic purpose of the text of official documents and its rapid implementation. The level of success of a speech act expressed in departmental documents depends on the accuracy and brevity of the text, the ability to set the intended purpose of the addressee, the correct choice of methodological units in the text.

In the formal style, the subordination of language units to a particular pragmatic goal statement is determined by the overall structure of the text. For example, in a job application, the speaker's desire to get a job is explained in full. However, there are also departmental working documents that use auxiliary devices for *-sh (-ish)* and *-sh (-ish)* in the text of the document in order to clearly express the pragmatic purpose.

At times, these auxiliary phrases become formal and standard. In particular, standard phrases such as "Granted to the workplace" and "Granted to the place of residence" used in the text of working documents, such as references, descriptions, indicate the purpose (information) of the document.

-sh (-ish) maqsadida used in some business documents, the auxiliary devices *-sh (-ish) uchun* reflect the purpose of the addressee, which is the basis for the formation of the document, rather than the intended purpose of the document. In this case, the purpose of the document is clear from the general text. For example, the following sentence in the recommendation section of the decree states: «*Ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini oshirish maqsadida shu yilning 20-dekabrigacha aniq takliflar ishlab chiqilsin. Mas'ul A.Ibrohimov*». (“*In order to increase production efficiency, specific proposals should be developed by December 20 this year. Responsible A.Ibrohimov*”).

It should be acknowledged that such departmental working papers express several pragmatic goals. In the given text, the main purpose of the addressee is to increase production efficiency. His recommendation to achieve this goal is the goal of the document. Thus, business documents of this type express two purposes of the addressee: the purpose on which the document is based, and the purpose for which the document is intended.

The core business orders are also a shining example of working papers that reflect such common pragmatic goals. They are required to clearly state the purpose of the command in the

introduction. In this case, one of the auxiliary devices *-sh (-ish) uchun, -sh (-ish) maqsadidais* used in the introductory part of the command text. For example, «Korxonaning ishlab chiqarish hajmini **kengaytirish maqsadida** B U YU R A M A N». (“**I O R D E R in order to expand** the production capacity of the enterprise”) [5].

The following sentence from the service letter (letter of request) also expresses various interrelated pragmatic goals: *Korxonamiz ishchisi N.Soliyevni malakasini oshirish maqsadida 1 oyga tajriba o'tashga qabul qilishingizni so'raymiz (We ask you to accept an employee of our company N. Soliev for a month internship in order to improve their skills).*

So, in the Uzbek language, every official working document serves a specific purpose. As K. Omonov noted, “The most important aspect of the nature of the official text is that it is focused on practice, that is, on the fulfillment of a pre-determined goal. The official text is always a pragmatic phenomenon that performs a practical function. So it comes to us as a complete system, as a complete message with its own content and devices.” [6, 21]

References

1. Аминов М., Мадвалиев А., Маҳкамов Н., Маҳмудов Н. Ишюритиш. 2-нашри. – Тошкент: Ўзбекистонмиллийэнциклопедияси, 2003. – Б. 279.
2. Почепцов О.Г. Основы прагматического описания предложения. – Киев: Вища школа, 1986. – С. 75.
3. Каримов Р. Тижоратхатларининглинговпрагматикаспекти: Филол. фан. бўй. фалс. док. (PhD) дисс. автореф. – Тошкент, 2018. – Б. 11.
4. Сафаров Ш. Прагмалингвистика. – Тошкент: ЎзбекистонМиллийэнциклопедияси, 2008. – Б. 82, 79.
5. Лутфуллаева Д. Мустақилликдавирасмийидоравийишуслужитараққиёти. – Тошкент. “Nodirabegim” нашриёти. 2020. 105 б.
6. Омонов К. Туркийрасмийуслужбингюзагакелишиватакомили (илкваўртаасрлар): Филол. фан. докт. ... дисс. автореф. – Тошкент, 2016. – Б. 21.
7. Davlatova R. Pragmatic analysis of the linguistic concept of person-referencing deixis and pronouns referring to it in the uzbek language. Journal of Critical Reviews. 2020. Vol 7. P.350-354.<https://www.scopus.com/sourceid/21100920227#tabs=0http://jcreview.com>
8. Lutfullaeva D., Saparniyazova M., Davlatova R. Criteria for creating a name in the uzbek language. Journal of critical reviews (JCR). 2020; 7(16) doi: [10.31838/jcr.07.16.403](https://doi.org/10.31838/jcr.07.16.403)
9. Rustamiy S. Typological peculiarities of science of balaghah, rhetoric and stylistics. *The Light of Islam*, 2018 (1). 16.
10. Shoaliev N. Literary expression of human and mystical perfection in SohrabSepehri's poetry. International Journal of Innovative Technologies in Social Science. Warsaw, 2019. 7(19). P. 11-20.
11. Nasirova M. Incomplete conjunction of words in the arabic grammar. *The Light of Islam: Vol. 2019. P. 95-130.*<https://uzjournals.edu.uz/iiiau/vol2019/iss4/15>.

12. Nizamova F. Письменные навыки в изучении языка // Приоритетные направления научных исследований. Материалы II международной научно-практической конференции (28 ноября 2019). – Даллас: Издательский центр ИУСЭР, 2019. – С.106-109. https://iupr.ru/28_noyabrya_2019_g/
13. Сайидирахимова Н. Тилнинг концептуалморфологики фодаплани (когнитив аспект). Филологические науки: состояние, перспективы, новые парадигмы исследований. II Международная научная конференция, посвященная 100-летию образования Республики Башкортостан и 110-летию создания Башкирского государственного университета. Том 1. – Уфа, 2019. – Б.154-163.
14. Nig'monov Abdulazizkhan. Rhythmic-syntactic parallelisms in old turkic poetry (by example of extract from “Devon lugati-t-turk”). The Light of Islam: Vol. 2020. Iss. 1, Article 26. Available at: <https://uzjournals.edu.uz/iiaw/vol2020/iss1/26>
15. Arifdjanov Z. T. The structure of Persian verbs and their role in word formation. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science. 2020. 07 (87). P.420-423. <http://T-Science.org>